

Synergizing total quality management and school climate: an empirical probe into performance in Pakistan's government schools

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ABSTRACT: According to the Sustainable Development Goals for the year 2020, quality education is the most important concern in all over the world, with it securing the fourth position among the SDGs. To satisfy the quality criteria, there should be a real mechanism in place to improve educational quality. Total Quality Management (TQM) emerges as a prominent methodology for enhancing educational quality, often linked with school climate to bolster overall school performance. As a result, precise documentation of TQM and school climate is needed in government schools. The objective of this empirical study is to determine the extent of Total Quality Management and assess the prevailing school climate in Pakistani government schools, along with examining the relationship between TQM and school climate. Additionally, it seeks to identify the specific TQM dimensions that predict the school climate. Using a quantitative approach, the study involved 367 secondary school teachers selected through stratified random sampling in the district of Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan. Statistical analysis using SPSS version 24 was employed to test the hypotheses. The study's findings reveal that high-performing schools exhibit a greater level of TQM implementation and a more positive school climate. Pearson correlation analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between TQM and school climate. Moreover, regression analysis highlights three key indicators of school performance: staff participation, top management commitment, and commitment to continuous improvement.

Keywords: Unveiling Educational Excellence, Total quality management (TQM), School Climate, Academic Performance

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1. Introduction

Total Quality Management is one of the tools that enhance the quality of education and improve the students' performance. Total Quality Management serves as a transformative catalyst, elevating the standard of education to unprecedented levels (Mahmood, 2020). In the era of globalisation, a quality education system is seen to be capable of producing a workforce with superior human attributes such as innovation, productivity, skills, competitiveness, resilience, and creativity (Mahmood, Pervez, Ismail, & Kanwal, 2023). The quality of school management significantly impacted various dimensions of school quality, including the quality of graduates, processes, assessments, content, facilities, infrastructure, financing, and overall management. However, the quality of teachers, educational staff, and facilities and infrastructure remained unclear due to unreliable testing results. (Kurniady, Susilana, Widodo, & Halimi, 2022). Cruz et al., (2016) affirm school management as a multifaceted responsibility, highlighting the key aspects of principal managerial performance, which include vision-mission-targets, learning curriculum and management, financial and budgeting management, school facility and infrastructure, student service management, community relations, and school improvement plans. Total Quality Management (TQM) entails the support towards the continuous attainment of teachers' job satisfaction using an integrated set of tools, techniques and trainings based on factors such as top management commitment, customer focus, involvement of staff, training and education, and continuous improvement (Mahmood, Akram, Ismail, & Zalli, 2023; Mahmood, Kanwal, & Pervez, 2023).

School climate as basically an attitude, beliefs, norms and values that leads a child, a teacher and an administrator to feel safe, satisfied and confident, comfort among the students, teachers as well as entire school (Mahmood, 2020). Thus, school is a place where teachers feel safe, are not sad, and take notice of their students' development, where principals feel confidence to work, kids feel secure and study hard, and where students gain healthy social ties in addition to academic learning (Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee, 2021). The school environment possesses the capability to enhance student achievement and reduce instances of behavioural problems and dropout rates (Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee, 2019). To put it differently, the "climate shapes the quality of interactions among students, parents, teachers, and school personnel, and mirrors the values, norms, and objectives of the school" (National School Climate Council, 2007). School climate encompasses nearly every aspect of the school environment, including interactions within the school community, the quality of teaching and learning, and the organization of the school. According to Goldberg (2002), school reform and student achievement must be evaluated by determining the relationships and interdependencies that affect the performance of systems, processes, and the people functioning within a school. Many variables affect educational processes and student achievement including school climate that consists of student relations, school resources, collaboration, teaching innovation, and teacher's ability to make decision, and above all, the lack of TQM execution (Mahmood et al., 2020).

Several studies found that TQM methods could not completely accomplish quality school goals unless a favourable school climate for learning and teaching was created. The goal of this study was to investigate the role of TQM practises in enhancing school performance and to see if TQM practises can predict school climate and hence improve school performance.

Research objectives

In general, this study aims to assess the degree of TQM practices in two different categories and to develop best practices of TQM in schools, organization and governance of educational institutes still as identifying factors of TQM which contributes towards school climate. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

- a. To assess the degree of "TQM practices" in two categories schools HP and LP".

- b. To investigate the level of “School climate” in two categories schools HP and LP”.
- c. To investigate the relationship between TQM and school climate.
- d. To determine the dimensions of “TQM can be a predictor to school climate”.

2. Literature Review

Total quality Management

Deming (1989) and Juran (1986) proposed TQM as a management philosophy that emphasises work quality. TQM has deep roots in industry, but it also has a significant influence on education. TQM is a systematic program that includes everyone and everything in the organization that focus on continuous improvement. The concept of TQM was first introduced by Professor Edward Deming as the father of TQM and Mahmood (2020) described as “TQM is a tool that enhances the quality of education by meeting customer needs and expectations by continually improving teacher quality, teaching methods and general management”. Moreover, the philosophy of TQM has also been supported by numerous researchers mainly Crosby (1979, 1984), Deming (1986), Ishikawa (1983, 1985), Juran (1988, 1989), Feigenbaum (1958-68), Ismail (2014), (Mahmood, 2020a) and Mahmood et al.,(2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022).

Based on the models and previous literature reviews mentioned above, researchers compared and identified the various dimensions used in all studies, and developed a framework using the dimensions of employee participation, continuous improvement, customer focus, top management engagement, and main-study training and education. Despite the fact that there are several types of TQM, the most common approaches used by researchers are as follows (Ahire, Golhar, & Waller, 1996; Anderson & Sohal, 1999; Baidoun & Zairi, 2003; Dutta & Sahney, 2016; Egido Gálvez, Fernández Cruz, & Fernández Díaz, 2016; Ghosh & Han Hua, 1996; Ismail, 2014; Mahmood, Ismail, Hafiz, et al., 2021; Mahmood & Ismail, 2018; Mahmood et al., 2019, 2020b; Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee, 2021; Prabhu, Appleby, Yarrow, & Mitchell, 2000; Prajogo, 2005; Prajogo & Cooper, 2010; Zhang, Waszink, & Wijngaard, 2000) are the following: 1. Top Management Commitment, 2. Customer Focus, 3. Training and Education, 4. Continuous Improvement and 5. Involvement of Staff.

Figure 1. Total Quality Management dimensions (Mahmood, 2020).

Therefore, these five elements will function as the principal facets of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices in this investigation, and thorough explanations of each will follow in the subsequent subsections.

School Climate

The climate model consists of four main factors that determine the characteristics of an effective school climate namely culture (assumptions, values, norms, belief system), ecology (buildings, equipment, facilities), social systems (command, administrative,

decision-making, planning and formal structure) and human social systems (skills, attitude, values and leadership) Mahmood (2020). School climate as basically an attitude, beliefs, norms and values that leads a child, a teacher and an administrator to feel safe, satisfied and confident, comfort among the students, teachers as well as entire school (Mahmood, Pervez, et al., 2023). The quality and qualities of school life, including objectives, values, interpersonal interactions, formal organisational structures, and organisational practises, are characterised as school climate (Clifford, Menon, Condon, & Hornung, 2012). The four categories of school quality were positively and significantly influenced by school atmosphere. School quality was achieved via engagement, empowerment and autonomy, inclusiveness and equity, and the utilisation of the school climate as an essential feature in school administration. Managerial performance on school quality was successfully mediated by school climate (Kurniady et al., 2022). Thus, school is a place where teachers feel safe, are not depressed, and take notice of their students' development, where administrators feel confidence to work, students feel secure and study hard, and where students gain healthy social relationships in addition to academic learning (Khan, Akram, Shams, & Mahmood, 2023; Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee, 2020).

Furthermore, other scholars have identified certain characteristics of a good school climate. The school climate, according to Wang and Degol (2016), is comprised of four components: safety, academics, institutional environment, and community. First, the academic environment emphasizes the education system's consistency like guidance, curriculum, professional development, and teachers' preparation. Second, inside the school, the community determines the consistency of the interpersonal relations. Third, safety focuses on the extent of the school's emotional and physical protection, as well as the incidence of regular, efficient and fair disciplinary practices. Ultimately, the institutional environment shows the organizational features such as composition of the organization, school infrastructure and environmental factors. Mutually, these four components encompass any aspect of the school setting that affects cognitive, behavioural, and psychological growth of the students. Studies by (Ismail, 2014; Mahmood et al., 2019, 2020; Raman, Chi Ling, & Khalid, 2015; M. T. Wang & Degol, 2016), have discovered that a good quality atmosphere defines the school's success. Johnson and Stevens (2007) studied the school atmosphere using five (5) main dimensions: cooperation, student interactions, school resources, decision making, and instructional innovation. Using this model of school atmosphere and past investigations, researchers established the theoretical basis for this study (Ismail, 2014; Lam, Poon, & Chin, 2008; Mahmood, 2020b; Mahmood et al., 2019, 2020; Prajogo & McDermott, 2005; Ranjan Kumar & Sankaran, 2007; M.-T. Wang & Degol, 2016).

Figure 2. School Climate dimensions (Johnson, Stevens, and Zvoch (2007).

3. Methods

The research design entails the methods and procedures to gather and analyze data (Creswell, 2014). This study could be a quantitative method approach was employed. The data was collected and analysed by using SPSS version 24.

Population and Sampling

This survey included 346 teachers from 20 different schools who were chosen at random. To explain the sample size, "Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sample size determination" was utilised. The population of the study, according to Creswell (2014), refers to the whole group involved in the study. The samples, on the other hand, are the representative elements of the population (Salant & Dillman, 1994). The study was performed on two types of secondary schools in Bahawalpur, Pakistan in 2 different categories schools.

Instruments

A questionnaire was used to collect data. The questionnaire is divided into three (3) sections. "Part A is about the respondents' backgrounds, Part B discusses the number of TQM processes (27 items), and Part C discusses school atmosphere (21 items on a 7-point Likert scale). The TQM practises questionnaire consisted of five distinct constructs: top management commitment, continuous improvement, customer focus, staff engagement, and training and education (Ismail, 2014; Mahmood, 2020b; Mahmood et al., 2019, 2020). The Likert scale has 21 items in 5 scales namely: collaboration (6 items), student relation (4 items), school resources (4 items), decision making (3) and teaching innovation (4 items). Therefore, in this research, a 7-point scale was employed; the Total Quality Management (TQM) instrument utilized was developed by Mahmood (2020). The School Climate instrument, adapted from Johson, Stevens, and Zvoch (2007), underwent validation and reliability assessments. Construct validity was ensured through Exploratory Factor Analysis, while reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding values ranging from 0.71 to 0.91. Measuring school performance involves coding by segmenting a 7-point scale into three categories. Low-performance schools are within the range of 1 to 2.33, medium-performance schools fall between 2.34 to 4.66, and high-performance schools are within the range of 4.67 to 7.

Data Analysis

The degree of TQM processes and the school climate were determined using descriptive analytic statistics. Correlational design is appropriate for evaluating complex patterns of relationships between measured variables (Stangor, 2011). To explore the association between the two variables, TQM processes and school climate, Pearson correlation was utilized. Finally, Regression analysis was used to discover which TQM factors had the most influence on the varsity school atmosphere.

4. Results

Level of TQM practices in HPS and LPS

In addressing this query, the investigators employed descriptive analysis to obtain a comprehensive mean value for each domain of TQM practices. Subsequently, they compared the mean values for classification and interpretation, determining the level of TQM practices based on various categories, as illustrated in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: “The level of TQM practices in high performance school (HPS) and lower performance school (LPS)”

TQM dimension	<u>Mean value (M) and standard deviation (SD)</u>			
	HPS	SD	LPS	SD
Top Management Commitment	5.17	0.77	3.19	0.40
Customer Focus	4.39	0.89	2.53	0.51
Training and Education	4.32	1.00	3.33	0.18
Involvement of Staff	5.05	1.03	3.34	0.29
Continuous Improvement	4.97	0.77	2.71	0.51
Total	4.87	0.74	3.07	0.27

Based on Table 1, the results show that the levels of TQM activities in high performance schools is greater with an average of 4.87, while the average values for each TQM dimension are high for top management commitment (M = 5.17, SD = 0.77), relatively high level for customer focus, (M = 4.39, SD = 0.89), also showed high level for training and education (M = 4.32, SD = 1.0), and the mean value showed high level for staff involvement (M = 5.05, SD = 1.03) and the mean value showed high level for continuous improvement (M = 4.97, SD = .77). As for the low performance schools, the findings show that all the TQM dimensions had relatively low means; top management commitment (M = 3.19, SD = 0.40), customer focus (M = 2.53, SD = 0.51), training and higher education (M = 3.33, SD = 0.18), staff involvement (M = 3.34, SD = 0.29) and continuous improvement (M = 2.71, SD = 0.51). Overall, the level of TQM practises in high-performing schools is high (M = 4.87, SD = 0.75), compared to the level of TQM practises in low-performing schools (M = 3.07, SD = 0.27). To summarise, the rate of TQM activities in high performing schools is higher than in low performing schools. To summarise, TQM helps to educational outcomes by ensuring that the school's performance is high if the number of TQM activities is high, and vice versa.

“Level of school climate in HPS and LPS”

Table 2: The level of School Climate in HPS and LPS

School Climate dimensions	<u>Mean value (M) and standard deviation (SD)</u>			
	HPS	SD	LPS	SD
Collaboration	4.76	0.80	3.56	0.39
Student Relation	4.88	0.80	3.50	0.41
School Resources	4.62	0.68	3.01	0.18
Decision Making	5.10	0.72	3.15	0.19
Teaching Innovation	4.93	0.77	3.01	0.27
Total	4.84	0.57	3.28	0.09

The results shown in Table 2 indicate the mean values for all the school climate dimensions in the high performance schools are relatively high as like collaboration (M = 4.76, SD = 0.80), relationship of students (M = 4.88, SD = 0.80), schools resources (M =

4.62, SD = 0.68), decision-making (mean = 5.10, SD = 0.72), and teaching innovation (M = 4.93, SD = 0.77). Overall, the mean for school climate is quite high in HPS (M = 4.84, SD = 0.57) as compared to that of LPS (M = 3.28, SD = 0.09). As a conclusion, school climate contributes to school performance whereby when the level of school climate is high, the performance of the school will also be high and vice versa.

The Relationship between TQM and school climate

The Pearson's correlation analysis was utilised to explore the association between TQM and school climate. The findings in Table 3 suggest that there is a substantial association between TQM and school climate. Because the value is near to one, the model is adequately described (Pallant, 2007). Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) ranging from -1 to +1 show whether there is a positive or negative association. The magnitude of the absolute value indicates the strength of the relationship between the variables. The positive strong association between TQM and school climate reveals that the higher the level of TQM practises, the higher the level of school climate, which leads to stronger school performance, as demonstrated in Table 3, where the value of $r = 0.94$, ($p 0.01$).

Table 3: Pearson correlation for TQM and school climate

Variables	School climate	
	Correlation value (r)	P
TQM practices	0.91	0.00

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The dimensions of “TQM as a predictors of school climate”.

Stepwise regression analysis was conducted to assess if the dimensions of TQM may be utilised to predict school climate or not. The data analysis revealed that only three (3) of the five (5) variables included in the regression model ($p < 0.05$) may operate as predictors of school environment, namely Top Management Commitment ($\beta = .29$, $p 0.05$), Continuous Improvement ($\beta = .32$, $p 0.05$), and Staff Involvement ($\beta = .38$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that just three (3) factors ($p < 0.05$) determine school atmosphere. These outcomes indicated that the R square value of these (3) dimensions are high with the school climate. The results showed that the top management commitment (R square value .88) was the highest value which showed that top management commitment dimension influence 88% towards school climate as compared to the others dimensions, while the involvement of staff has the second strongest relationship with school climate and continuous improvement has less influence than the other two dimensions with the (R square value .80). Hence, the result shows that TQM as a predictor of school climate and rejects the null hypothesis. Table 4 below shows the results of the analysis regression.

Table 4: Regression analysis results of the TQM dimensions over School Climate

Variables	B	Beta	R	R2	Adj.R2	T	p
Continuous Improvement	.21	.32	.86	.80	.80	7.35	0.00
Involvement of Staff	.28	.38	.93	.87	.86	11.20	0.00
Top Management Commitment	.21	.29	.94	.88	.88	7.17	.000
Constant	1.17					16.86	0.00

The standard error: 0.28. All three of these dimensions contribute as much as 89% of the variance of TQM practices

Regression equations involved are as follows:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + \dots + b_nx_n$$

Y (Dependent) = 1.17 (constant) + 0.21(Continuous improvement) + 0.28(Involvement of staff) + 0.21(Top management commitment).

Results of the study indicated the predictor variable namely TQM dimensions which is included in the regression model at $p < .05$. It demonstrates that TQM practises are substantial predictors of school climate ($\beta = .38$, $p < 0.05$) and one of the factors contributing to school climate, accounting for 90% of the variation in the change in school climate. These findings corroborate those of Marshall, Pritchard, and Gunderson (2007), Paul (1998), Ismail (2014), and (Mahmood et al., (2020) who indicated that TQM is a contributor to school climate. The results of their study showed that TQM implementation will contribute to a positive school climate.

This study found that only three out of the five variables could be the predictors of school climate namely continuous improvement ($\beta = .32$, $p < 0.05$), involvement of staff ($\beta = .38$, $p < 0.05$) and top management commitment ($\beta = .32$, $p < 0.05$). These factors are the predictors of school climate, contributing 89% of the variation in the criterion variable of school climate. As a consequence of the findings, it was determined that in order to raise the level of school environment, on-going improvement must be prioritised. Meanwhile, the dimensions of customer focus as well as training and education are not predictors of school climate. The findings convincingly reject the null hypothesis that TQM is not a predictor of school climate. Furthermore, the findings are equivalent to those of Shire et al. (1999) and Ismail (2014), indicating that top management commitment is a key element in TQM adoption. Furthermore, it is congruent with Fullan's (2002) leadership theory, which states that change is achievable if it originates from the leader. It therefore clearly indicates that the effective implementation of TQM principles inside a business is dependent on the commitment of senior management.

5. Discussion

Overall, the level of TQM procedures varied between two categories. This finding is consistent with that of Raman, Chi Ling, and Khalid (2015) and Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee (2020) who stated that the quality of education in schools is influenced by the practice of TQM. In other words, when the level of TQM practice is high, the academic performance of the schools will be high as well. These findings also consistent with Manna, Calzone, Adinolfi, and Palumbo (2019) and Mahmood, Ismail, & Omar Fauzee (2020) who stated that improvements in high school performance and teaching can only be achieved with the implementation of the quality management approach. Hence, the proper implementation of TQM practices in schools leads to a high level of school performance and academic achievement as compared to schools that neglect to do so.

To sum up, in high performance schools, the rate of school climate activities is high relative to that of low performance schools. To conclude, school climate contributes to educational outcomes, whereby the school's performance would also be high if the amount of school climate activities is high, and the other way round. For every aspect of the TQM practices and school climate, the results of Pearson correlation test showed a positive significant relationship between the TQM practices and the school climate. These results also support the idea that when the management structure is run by a good manager, the chairman can develop a vision and goal to help and execute the organization (Mahmood, Ismail, & Mdzalli, 2022). Thus, the subordinates are clear on the organization's direction and are satisfied with their work due to the moral support given by the top management or head of department. This close relationship will prevent feelings of prejudice and hesitation towards each other. Therefore, it is crucial to build an organizational climate that is open (Fourie, 2018; Hoy, Miskel, & Tarter, 2012; Kean, Kannan, & Piaw, 2017).

The dedication of senior management and leadership is a key aspect in determining the efficacy of TQM processes in any firm. Quality improvement requires comprehensive modifications that encompass fundamental, philosophical, structural, and

work methods. These reforms can only be implemented with the strong backing of management, particularly higher management, which is the true policymaker. Quality policy formulation and the construction of a quality management system are two steps that reflect senior management commitment to TQM (Das et al., 2008; Das et al., 2008; Shire et al., 1999).

These findings are supported the findings of Malinen and Savolainen (2016) that when senior management is devoted to quality, the vision and purpose are supported in terms of materials, equipment, and subordinates (Goetsch & Davis, 2003; Malinen & Savolainen, 2016). When the subordinates are clear about which direction to go, they will enjoy doing their tasks. This close relationship will prevent feelings of prejudice and hesitation towards each other. Therefore, it is essential to build an open organizational climate (Dutta & Sahney, 2016; Hoy & Miskel, 1991).

These findings also support the findings of Kunnanatt (2007) that the involvement of staff from various levels and stages can create team spirit. In other words, the involvement of staff at all levels will lead to the successful implementation of TQM in an organization. Therefore, when employees 'are involved in decision-making concerning the organization's key agendas, they gain a sense of responsibility and thus are motivated to contribute more in work. Feeling a sense of belonging will generate commitment and satisfaction in work which will eventually form a healthy climate (Fourie, 2018; Gharakhani, Rahmati, Farrokhi, & Farahmandian, 2013).

Similarly, from the dimensions of continuous improvement, many studies (Das et al., 2008; Juran & Gryna, 1993; Kean et al., 2018; Prajogo & McDermott, 2005) found that the continuous improvements implemented in an organization is key to its success and contribute to its successful implementation of TQM practices. Continuous improvement will lead to organizational efficiency and effectiveness, which in turn leads to job satisfaction. This ultimately leads to the creation of a healthy climate (Gharakhani et al., 2013).

Hence, the outcomes of this research study have shown that the continuous improvement, involvement of staff and top management commitment are critical predictors of school climate which is in line with the findings in previous studies, as stated above.

The study's findings validate TQM's teaching in education by showing a fantastic school model that connects the size of two variables, TQM practices and school climate, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Excellent School Model

Limitation and Future Perspective

This study, however, is limited to two different categories schools in Bahawalpur, Punjab. For this reason, it is suggested that further study be conducted throughout Pakistan in the future to confirm the best output. Future study should look at the impact of teachers leadership styles on TQM activities in schools.

6. Conclusions

The research outcomes underscore the positive impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) on school climate, contributing significantly to the overall enhancement of school quality. It's noteworthy to mention that the application of TQM practices differs between schools categorized as "high" and "low." These variations illuminate the need for tailored strategies to effectively implement TQM across diverse educational settings.

In conclusion, the study provides actionable recommendations for senior school administrators aimed at refining programs and training courses. The goal is to facilitate the seamless integration of TQM principles into school practices. It is particularly emphasized that a robust commitment from top management is pivotal in transforming the theoretical model into practical reality within educational institutions. This commitment is seen as a powerful catalyst for the rapid and effective improvement of student, teacher, and overall school performance.

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